

Propulsion in space without propellant

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Abstract

This paper presents an engine that can create propulsion without the use of propellants

1 Introduction

Conventional rockets are known to be inefficient for use in space vehicles. For chemical propulsion, the exhaust speed is between 2 km/s and 4.9 km/s . In engines with plasma propulsion exhaust speeds between 20 and 60 km/s are achieved. For missions beyond the Solar System, new forms of propulsion are needed. Concepts such as EmDrive [1], [2], [3] and Mach-Effect-Thruster [4], [5], [6], [7] are being examined and experimentally tested [8], [9], [10].

This paper presents an engine that can create propulsion without the use of propellants. The idea is to use the space-time and its contained mass-energy as a support to move through it efficiently. Mach's conjecture says "mass there influences inertia here". In this case the mass there influences the inertia of the component C of the engine and this inertia becomes a support point for the movement in the space of the components A and B of the engine in a given direction $y(t)$, where t is the time, and, simultaneous and symmetrically, the inertia of the components A and B become support points for the movement the component C in the same direction $y(t)$.

2 The engine

2.1 Description

The Figure 1 shows the top and lateral view of the engine which is formed of two main parts. The first part is formed by three arms. The component A and the rod S_A constitute the first arm, the components B and S_B constitute the second arm and the components C and S_C the third arm. S_A and S_B are parallel all the time. The mass of C is twice the mass of A and the mass of B is equal to the mass of A . The masses of A , B and C , denoted respectively by m_A , m_B and m_C , are concentrated in their geometrical centers. The masses of S_A , S_B and S_C are denoted respectively by m_{S_A} , m_{S_B} and m_{S_C} . The masses of the rods are such that

$$m_{S_A} = m_{S_B} = m_{S_C} \lll m_A \quad (1)$$

The three rods are rigid and have the same dimensions.

The second main part, shown in red in the Figure 1, is detailed in the Figures 2 and 3. The axis E has two parts. One of the parts of the E and R_A form a component (one part is attached to the other part), the second part of E and R_B form the other component and the Figure 2 shows one of these components. We call the part shown in red in Figure 1 *rotor*. The third part of the rotor is R_C . As shown in the Figure (2) there are holes in each of the three rotor parts through which the rods S_A , S_B and S_C slide without friction.

The three parts A , B and C rotate around the central axis e , presented in the Figure 1, with the same angular velocity $|\omega(t)|$. The distances of the center of mass of A , B and C to the central axis e are equal to r . For an observer located in o (see the top view of the Figure 1) the part C rotates clockwise and A and B rotate counterclockwise.

The sum of the masses of the E , R_A , R_B and R_C , denoted by m_{rotor} , is

$$m_{rotor} \lll m_A \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Top and lateral view of the engine at t_0

Figure 2: The rotor

Figure 3: A component of the rotor

2.2 Operation

The Figure 4 presents the engine at the instant t_0 the arms A , B and C are at rest in respect to the inertial frame S . We assume that (i) in the time interval (t_0, t_1) the module of the angular speed $\omega(t)$ increases from 0 to $|\omega(t_1)|$ and (ii) in the same interval the velocities of A , B and C , denoted by $v_A(t)$, $v_B(t)$ and $v_C(t)$ increase from 0 to $v_A(t_1)$, $v_B(t_1)$ and $v_C(t_1)$ such that

$$v_A(t_1) = v_{Ax}(t_1) = v_B(t_1) = v_{Bx}(t_1) \quad (3)$$

and

$$v_C(t_1) = v_{Cx}(t_1) = -v_A(t_1) \quad (4)$$

the subscript x refers to the positive direction of the axis- x of the inertial frame S and the time interval (t_0, t_1) is very small.

The angular speed $\omega(t)$ of A remains constant from t_1 to t_2 . At t_2 the component of $v_{Ax}(t)$ becomes equal to Δv_{Ax} , a negative value, where

$$|\Delta v_{Ax}| = v_{Ax}(t_1) \quad (5)$$

The Figure 5 presents the engine at the instant t_2 .

Figure 4: Top and lateral view of the engine at t_1

Figure 5: Top and lateral view of the engine at t_2

Figure 6: Top and lateral view of the engine at t_3

The control system (CS) of the engine moves the three arms to the position in relation to the rotor found in t_3 . From t_2 to t_3 the speed $v_{Ax}(t)$ is maintained equal to $|\Delta v_{Ax}|$. The Figure 6 presents the engine at t_3 .

From t_3 to t_4 the CS moves the three arms to put the engine at the position found in Figure 7. From t_4 to t_5 the control system rotates C counterclockwise and rotate A and B clockwise.

$$t_5 - t_3 \lll t_3 - t_2 \quad (6)$$

At t_5 the engine can initiate a new cycle starting from a state equivalent to that found in t_1 .

Figure 7: Top and lateral view of the engine at t_4

The Figure 8 shows A at a given position and time instant. p is the angle formed by the axis of the rod R_A and its projection on the plane- xz .

The torque applied by the rotor on A and B is counterbalanced by the torque applied by the rotor on C . The Figure 9 shows at the same instant used for the Figure 8 the velocity $v_{TA}(t)$, resulting from the applied torque. The velocity $v_{TA}(t)$ is decomposed in two components as shows the figure. We have

$$v_{Ax}(t) = v_A(t_1) - v_{TA}(t) \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - p\right) \quad (7)$$

and

$$v_{Ay}(t) = v_{TA}(t) \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - p\right) \quad (8)$$

Figure 8: A at a given position and time instant

with

$$v_{AT}(t) = \omega(t) l_{ref} \frac{t}{t_{max}} \quad (9)$$

where l_{ref} is a reference length of the rods R_A , R_B and R_C in which the rotor moves during the engine operation and t_{max} is the maximum time for a cycle of the engine.

Figure 9: Components of the speed of A

2.3 Performance

Let the set of specifications be

$$m_A = m_B = \frac{m_C}{2} = 1 \text{ [kg]} \quad (10)$$

$$t_{max} = 0.25 \text{ [s]} \quad (11)$$

$$t_0 = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$t_1 - t_0 \lll t_{max} \quad (13)$$

$$\omega(t_0) = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$\omega(t_1) = 120\pi \text{ [rad s}^{-1}\text{]} \quad (15)$$

$$v_A(t_1) = v_{Ax}(t_1) = 40 [m s^{-1}] \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta v_{Ax}(t_2) = f_{actor} v_{Ax}(t_1) \quad (17)$$

$$f_{actor} = 1 \quad (18)$$

$$l_{ref} = 1 [m] \quad (19)$$

$$x_A(t_0) = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$y_A(t_0) = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$d \lll l_{ref} \quad (22)$$

The distance d is shown in the Figure 10.

Figure 10: d and l_{ref}

The blue curve in the Figures 11 presents the trajectory of A in the plane- xy . This curve ends at the time $t_3 = 0.2461 s$, when $x_A(t_3) = x_A(t_0)$, at this instant the angle p shown in Figures 8 and 9 is 22.147° and $y_A(t_3) = 43.97 m$.

Figure 11: Trajectory of A in the plane- xy for $f_{actor} = 1$

The curves blue, brown, green and red in the Figure 12 are obtained with the specifications above given, except (12) and (18), t_{max} is 1 s and the values of f_{actor} are 1, $\frac{13}{10}$, 2 and 4 respectively.

The Figures 13 and 14 present $x_A(t)$ and $y_A(t)$ from t_0 to t_3 for the specifications used for Figure 11.

The Figure 15 presents $v_{Ax}(t)$ from t_0 to t_3 for the specifications given from (10) to (22), this component of $v_A(t)$ crosses the axis- x at 0.1303 s. Changing the value of f_{actor} to $\frac{13}{10}$ or 2 or 4, we found that the component of $v_{Ax}(t)$ crosses the axis- x at 0.1303 s too. Figure 16.

The Figure 17 presents $v_{Ay}(t)$ from t_0 to t_3 for the specifications given from (10) to (17) and from (19) to (22) and the f_{actor} equal to $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{10}$, $\frac{1}{20}$ and $\frac{1}{40}$. The four curves overlap. The Figure

Figure 12: Trajectory of A in the plane- xy

Figure 13: Trajectory $x_A(t)$

Figure 14: Trajectory $y_A(t)$

Figure 15: Velocity $v_{Ax}(t)$

Figure 16: Velocity $v_{Ax}(t)$

18 shows the case for $f_{actor} = 1$ and $t_{max} = 0.25$, in this figure for $t = 0.1313$ s the value of v_{Ay} is 193.6 $m.s^{-1}$. The acceleration of A is approximately

$$a_{Ay}(t_{1,3}) = \frac{193.6}{0.1313} [m.s^{-2}] = 1474 [m.s^{-2}] \quad (23)$$

and assuming that $t_4 = 0.25$ s we obtain per cycle

$$a_{Ay}(t_{1,4}) = \frac{193.6}{0.25} [m.s^{-2}] = 774.4 [m.s^{-2}] \quad (24)$$

Figure 17: Velocity $v_{Ay}(t)$

Figure 18: Velocity $v_{Ay}(t)$ for $f_{actor} = 1$

Using the specifications given from (10) to (22) the Figure 19 shows that for $t = 0.25$ s we have $e_{kAx} = 800$ J . The kinetic energy $e_{kAx}(t_5)$ is used for the next cycle of the engine. The Figure 20 presents the component of the kinetic energy in the axis- y direction. For $t = 0.1313$ s we obtain $e_{cAy}(t) = 18752$ J , therefore the power consumed by the engine is

$$\frac{18752}{0.2500} W = 7.501 \times 10^4 W \quad (25)$$

Figure 19: Kinetic energy $e_{kAx}(t)$

Figure 20: Kinetic energy $e_{kAy}(t)$

The length of the rods used in the engine operation is given in the Figure 21 for the specifications from (10) to (22). This length is obtained with

$$\frac{x(t) - x(t_0)}{\cos(p(t))} \quad (26)$$

Figure 21: The length of the rods used

As assumed, the mass of the engine is 4 kg. Let the engine be installed in a spacecraft and the total mass of the vehicle be such that the acceleration of the engine (and of the spacecraft) is reduced from (24) to g . In this case the mass of the vehicle is

$$\frac{774.4 [m.s^{-2}]}{9.80665 [m.s^{-2}]} \times 4 kg = 315.9 [kg] \quad (27)$$

Then starting at rest in the referential S , after one day the speed of the nave is

$$(24 \times 60 \times 60) \times 9.80665 [m.s^{-2}] = 3.050 \times 10^6 [km.h^{-1}] \quad (28)$$

When the nave reaches the speed given in (28) the energy consumed by the engine is $6.481 \times 10^9 J$. Nuclear energy is necessary, a quantity of mass equal to $7.211 \times 10^{-8} kg$ needs to be converted into the energy consumed by the engine in a day. The fission of approximately $8.816 \times 10^{-5} kg$ of U-235 provides the energy consumed.

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